

Analysis of 'Mariposa' Luluk HF's Mega Best-Seller Novel in Reception Study by Tania Intan

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Abstract

Study this talk about reception reader of the mega best-selling novel entitled Mariposa by Luluk HF. The objective study is to decipher response readers, describe the horizon of hope readers, as well display factors reason the difference between response and horizon of hope reader novels.

Keywords: *literary reception, response readers the horizon of hope, mariposa*

INTRODUCTION

Mariposa's novel which has been read more than 100 million times or mentioned in other sources about 130 million times, is created by seobyrom writer Luluk HF. Creation fiction teenagers the read, especially by Wattpad users and get many comments positive from them. When published Becomes the book by Coconut Books, Mariposa was a success selling up to 8,000 copies in a day.

Mariposa comes from the language Spanish meaning ' butterfly . ' by philosophy, butterflies, in general, will run when chased, however, will come closer moments left. Mariposa tells about the pursuit figure main woman named Acha very like a man named Iqbal whose behavior resembles difficult butterfly arrested.

METHOD

This analytical study uses a qualitative descriptive method because it explains a social event in how the author analyzes the paper. This method is considered by the author to be very important because this method will display a form of explanation related to a phenomenon being studied and interpreted in the context and concept of writing. Of course, in carrying out this research, the author uses a hermeneutic approach because the analysis of this paper will be studied by interpreting the contents and adjusting to the events that occurred at that time. Type study this utilize strength deep analysis as well as detailed, at once broad and holistic because of that, power reason is the only source of power for analyzing the whole research process.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings in this study talk about four things, that is synopsis story, reader response, reader horizon, and causal factors difference or conformity horizon expectations reader with the novel Mariposa.

Moving storyline progressive without flashback like addressed for support idea determination unyielding back off from figure ah. Tendency narration siding with the characters teenager woman that brought by a third person outside story that knows all things that happen to every character.

The purpose of this paper analysis in the form of a discussion is to give information to readers for join explore natural the minds of the characters and can understand reason from their behavior. Because telling about conflict romances teenagers and read more a lot by teenagers, then language and style The writing used also tends to no raw informal, and casual. Characters featured teenagers live in acha big that each other use the “ me – lo” greeting that shows the existence of familiarity and friendship between them.

After experiencing repeated rejections from Iqbal, Acha decides to give up and begins to consider Juna, who likes him. That's when Iqbal felt something was missing from him. The ending shows that after going through various strange events, Iqbal realizes that he likes Acha, but finds it difficult to express it. Mariposa's story is closed according to the reader's desire to unite Acha and Iqbal in a romantic relationship.

CONCLUSION

For how the author subjectively sees from the analysis of the paper that the expectations horizon of most readers does not match the reality presented by Mariposa's novel. Respondents stated that the reason for their interest in reading the novel was because of a friend's recommendation as well as the claims of the book publisher and Wattpad who called Mariposa a mega best-seller. After reading, the respondents realized that hyperbolic labeling is nothing but a mere form of promotion and sales strategy so it does not guarantee the quality of the work. In the context of the hope horizon, it was also revealed that the reader's interest was triggered by the discourse that the Mariposa novel would be filmed and played by well-known artists among teenagers.

Meanwhile, the factors that cause differences in the responses and horizons of readers' expectations found in this study are due to differences in knowledge of literature, knowledge of life, and experience of reading literary works. This research has not been fully completed. There are still other research gaps that can be continued, such as the results of the conversion of the novel into a film and the audience's reception of the organization's work.

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